

ISic3016

I.Sicily inscription 3016

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

dedication

Material

limestone

Object

rock

face

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

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Autopsy

2006.04; 2013.10.02

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)**Place of origin (modern)**

Buscemi

Provenance**Coordinates**

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 19225

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI332325

1. ἱερεῖς ²⁷HPHΔΙΣ²⁷

2.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645364

PHI 332325

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum*

graecum. At 42.0826

undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-.

Notizie degli scavi di antichità. *Notizie degli scavi di antichità*. At 464 no.14

Manganaro, G. 1992. Iscrizioni "rupestri" di Sicilia. In Gasperini, L.(eds.), *Rupes loquentes: atti del convegno internazionale di studio sulle iscrizioni rupestri di età romana in Italia. Roma - Bomarzo 13-15.X.1989*. Rome. pp. 447-501. At 457 no.2

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